

Social Transformation for Water Stewardship
through Scaling Up Citizen Science

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Executive Summary

This deliverable report summarizes the detailed plan for actions aimed at engaging and mobilising the immediate and extended communities and stakeholders towards achieving the objectives of the project. The relevant stakeholders are identified for each WP.

In particular, the report outlines 1) strategies for engagement through workshops, webinars, and online platforms to facilitate content sharing, communication, and collaboration, and 2) actions targeted to specific audiences categorized into four clusters.

Introduction

1. OTTERS project overview

The OTTERS project aims to promote societal transformation for marine and freshwater stewardship through scaling up citizen science.

OTTERS will support the coordination of EU citizen science initiatives focused on marine and freshwater ecosystems, aiming to:

- Accelerate the creation and adoption of technical, legal, and ethical standards for citizen science protocols and methods.
- Examine the effectiveness of citizen science in societal transformation towards sustainable aquatic ecosystem stewardship.
- Pilot cross-community, watershed-based Spring-to-Sea Stewardship Campaigns.
- Promote the scaling up of citizen science initiatives through clustering different initiatives, dissemination of the outcomes and results.

The key outcomes will be:

- i) Clustering initiatives and adoption of new standards,
- ii) Preparation and promotion of toolkits and digital applications to aid in monitoring for the requirements of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD),
- iii) Scaled up collection of real-time recordings,
- iv) Increased knowledge and care for healthy freshwater and marine ecosystems,
- v) Increased understanding on the effectiveness of citizen science,
- vi) Integration and use of guidelines for freshwater and marine stewardship campaigns through EU policies and program,
- vii) Enhanced science-policy dialogue.

1.1 OTTERS objectives

Citizen science is a tool for mass-scale, decentralised knowledge generation that can accelerate research progress and provide valuable insights that might not have been possible with traditional scientific approaches. Citizen science is also a tool to democratise access to research, and to empower individuals to contribute to addressing societal and environmental changes, to foster citizen engagement and stewardship of the natural environment, including the marine and freshwater domains.

To be successful, citizen science initiatives must have standardised methods for data collection that are in line with policy, scientific standards, and pre-existing or large-scale/long-term data collection initiatives, as well as overcome institutional and ethical challenges. Data standards will facilitate data exchange through web service protocols, leading to multi-scale interoperability through the effective integration into international environmental databases. Furthermore, it will also increase the use of citizen science generated data by the scientific community, policy and decision makers, as well as other interest groups. Moreover, to achieve the social

transformation goals, citizen science initiatives need to be embedded into narratives and sustained campaigns that aim not only to change minds but also hearts, as well as generate data for research or monitoring purposes. To meet this challenge, **OTTERS** seeks to facilitate EU-funded citizen science initiatives to:

- **Accelerate the co-creation of standards** for citizen science protocols and methods, particularly in marine and freshwater domains. These standards will enhance the scientific rigour, the usability of the data, the policy relevance, increased social acceptability and adoption, and institutional embeddedness of citizen science. This will ultimately contribute to adding a special citizen-generated data layer, including for example real-time recordings of discharges and levels of pollutants and litter for different sites, to be harmonised and made publicly available through EMODnet and hence the European Digital Twin Ocean, and aligned with the Destination Earth initiative of the Digital Europe program.
- **Demonstrate the effective embedding of citizen science in initiatives seeking societal transformation for sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems** to not only generate data and knowledge but also contribute to changing hearts, increasing care and investment for marine and freshwater ecosystems and fostering a sense of agency.
- **Assess the effectiveness of citizen science** for research and innovation, the impact of citizen science campaigns on citizen behaviour and their epistemic relation with marine and freshwater environments, and assess the contribution of specific stakeholders, such as fishing communities, sailors, divers, schools, local associations (cultural, environmental and recreational), etc. All work will be developed, presented and carried out with an inclusive mindset, aiming to achieve a fair representation of society in terms of gender, age, background and other frequent biases.
- **Promote scaling up of citizen science initiatives** through clustering of different initiatives, and disseminate the outcomes and results of the above-mentioned objectives, as well as EU-funded initiatives that mobilise and empower citizens to take actions to improve the monitoring of the health of the ocean and freshwater ecosystems and to act against pollution, biodiversity loss and further human impacts. Moreover, to promote digital applications and testing kits enabling citizens to collect data and observations; and lastly, to promote (digital) data collection and participatory research approaches involving citizens for the monitoring and restoration of aquatic ecosystems.

1.2 OTTERS Stakeholders and End-Users

For effective and wide-reaching communication and dissemination, the target groups i.e. the stakeholders and end-users need to be defined apriori. OTTERS will use the term stakeholder to mean any person (or legal entity) with an interest or stake in the project's results and outcomes, or who is directly or indirectly affected by them. The term end-users is used for persons/groups who have an interest in the exploitation of OTTERS results and outcomes. Stakeholders often have different perspectives, priorities, and levels of influence, which can

shape their expectations and interactions with the project or organisation. The wider public refers to any other person, entity, group or organisation who has an interest in any aspect of the OTTERS project or EU HE funding.

Stakeholder groups differ for each WP of the project. Correspondingly, Table 1 below details identified stakeholder groups relevant for each WP:

Table 1: Relevant stakeholders to be engaged and mobilised for each work package of the OTTERS project.

Work Package No	Work Package Name	Relevant stakeholders
WP1	Standardisation of protocols and methods for water-related citizen science	Policy-makers, citizens science projects/initiatives, academics, experts (data managers / repositories, technology developers)
WP2	Deepening understanding of the effectiveness of citizen science campaigns in marine and freshwater domains	Academics, policymakers, civil society
WP3	Changing Hearts and Minds – Co-designing transformational, citizen science campaigns for Spring-to-Sea Stewardship and supporting clustering of existing CS initiatives under the relevant campaign	Citizens science projects/initiatives, civil society, school educators, students, relevant Mission Ocean projects and signatories
WP4	Education and capacity building	School educators
WP5	Communication and dissemination	Mission Ocean signatories, citizen science initiatives/projects, school educators, academics, relevant experts, technology developers.
WP6	Project Management	N/A
WP7	Ethics requirements	N/A

Interaction and consultation with end-users, stakeholders, and the wider public in the design and development of OTTERS outcomes is a key aspect of the project. This approach is fundamental to ensure that the OTTERS project results and outcomes are fit-for-purpose and

sustainable after the end of the project. Achieving this the project has already developed and published a Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) [\[link\]](#) to reach, engage with and inform stakeholders, to change behaviour, and ultimately ensure the long-term sustainability of the project results and outcomes.

In addition, the Mobilisation and Action Plan (this document) further establishes the roadmap to engaging and mobilising the immediate and extended communities and stakeholders towards achieving the objectives of the project.

1.3 OTTERS Mobilisation and Action Plan objectives

The report seeks to provide a detailed blueprint for mobilising the community, relevant projects and stakeholders around the OTTERS project. It emphasises the importance of engagement, data collection and management, standardisation of efforts, to pave the way towards extensive citizen data exploitation in achieving the overarching goal of the Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030.

Engagement is a key component of the OTTERS project as it entails the active involvement of community members and stakeholders in the project's activities. The report outlines strategies for engagement, such as organising workshops, webinars, and online platforms to facilitate content sharing, communication, and collaboration. The approach is designed to build a sense of ownership and commitment among stakeholders, encouraging them to actively participate in the project and add information and value to it.

Data collection and communication are essential aspects of the OTTERS project as they provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of citizen science initiatives in promoting environmental stewardship. This document comes as a supplement to the OTTERS Data Management Plan [\[link\]](#) and the aforementioned Outreach, Communication, and Dissemination Plan, to better define the approach and steps to be taken by the project in not just communicating to its audience but engaging them, building a living community and fostering agency towards achieving water stewardship. In many ways, the project's modus operandi will mimic its own objectives of changing hearts and minds.

The report discusses methods and tools for collecting and analysing data from citizen science initiatives, ensuring that the data collected is accurate, reliable, and relevant to the project's objectives. By analysing this data, the project can evaluate the impact of citizen science on societal transformation and identify areas for improvement.

The broader goal of the OTTERS project is to foster societal transformation towards environmental stewardship. This goal is ambitious but achievable through targeted strategies and actions outlined in the report. By mobilising the community and stakeholders, collecting and analysing data, and implementing the findings, the project can make significant strides towards achieving this goal.

In conclusion, the report provides a comprehensive plan for mobilising the community and stakeholders around the OTTERS project. By following the strategies outlined in the report, the

project can effectively foster societal transformation towards environmental stewardship.

2. Mobilisation strategies

To effectively engage and mobilise relevant stakeholders, the OTTERS project will employ a variety of strategies, including workshops, seminars, participation in conferences, fora, and international events, as well as online platforms. These strategies are designed to build ownership and commitment among stakeholders, ensuring their active participation and support for the project's objectives.

Workshops will be organised to provide stakeholders with a platform to discuss key issues related to marine and freshwater stewardship. These workshops will feature presentations from experts in the field, interactive discussions, and hands-on activities to engage participants and encourage collaboration. By fostering open dialogue and sharing of ideas, workshops will help build a sense of ownership among stakeholders, as they will feel that their input is valued and considered in the decision-making process.

Seminars will also play a crucial role in engaging stakeholders and mobilising support for the OTTERS project. These seminars will focus on raising awareness about the importance of environmental stewardship and the role of citizen science in achieving this goal, in addition to shedding light on relevant ongoing efforts in an effort to promote synergies and joint activities. By featuring inspiring speakers and thought-provoking presentations, seminars will inspire stakeholders to take action and become actively involved in citizen science projects in the water domain.

OTTERS consortium members, many of whom are already active in academic and civil society circles, will be attending and presenting the project's outcomes and findings in relevant international conferences and events. OTTERS will also investigate possibilities of organising side-events, workshops, and co-designing opportunities to engage and mobilise those attending in discussions of standardisation, impact, and scaling up of citizen participation in freshwater and marine domains. Furthermore, involvement in writing conference proceedings and other joint publications will help mobilise a wider audience, beyond those who could attend the events.

In addition to workshops and seminars, online platforms will be utilised to engage stakeholders and facilitate communication. These platforms will provide a forum for stakeholders to share information, collaborate on projects, and stay updated on the latest developments related to the OTTERS project. By leveraging the power of technology, online platforms will enable stakeholders to participate in the project from anywhere in the world, ensuring that their voices are heard and their contributions are valued. To this aim, OTTERS is developing the Citizen Science Resource Hub to be eventually added to ECSA's website as a repository of all relevant material for standardising and scaling up of citizen science in the water domain. Additionally, the project's social media channels will be used to reach a wider audience to disseminate upcoming project events, news and materials produced. On social media, relevant tags and hashtags will be used to engage the wider Mission Ocean community and cross-posts with other relevant Mission CSAs (e.g. PREP4BLUE, BlueMissionMed, Blue Mission Atlantic & Arctic,

BlueMissionBANOS, EcoDaLLi, DaWetRest among others) will be used to reach the maximum number of stakeholders. More information on dissemination strategies can be found in the OTTERS Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP).

Building ownership and commitment among stakeholders is a critical component of the OTTERS project's success. To achieve this, the project will implement a range of initiatives, including stakeholder consultations, partnership agreements, and recognition programs. Stakeholder consultations will involve co-designing the decision-making process, ensuring that views and opinions of key players are taken into account when developing project plans and strategies.

Partnership agreements will be established with key stakeholders, including government agencies, non-profit organisations, and community groups. These agreements will outline the roles and responsibilities of each partner, ensuring that everyone is aligned with the project's objectives and committed to achieving them. By formalising these partnerships, the project will build a strong network of supporters who are invested in its success.

Recognition programs will acknowledge and highlight successful initiatives that can be viewed as model examples to be replicated elsewhere or on a larger scale. These programs will highlight the achievements of individuals and organisations that have made significant contributions to citizen science and Mission Ocean objectives, inspiring others to get involved and contribute their time and resources. By recognizing and celebrating the efforts of stakeholders, the project will foster a sense of pride and ownership among participants, ensuring their continued commitment to the project's objectives.

In conclusion, the OTTERS project will employ a range of strategies to engage and mobilise stakeholders, including workshops, seminars, and online platforms. By building ownership and commitment among stakeholders, the project will ensure their active participation and support, driving the project's success and fostering societal transformation towards environmental stewardship.

3. Action Plan

The OTTERS project will be undertaking a number of different initiatives to help drive societal transformation towards a community with solid water stewardship principles and commitments. These actions, targeted to specific audiences, can be categorised into the following clusters:

1. Promoting the standardisation of methods used by citizen-scientists to capture data on aquatic environments and subsequent data management and transfer.
2. Increasing ocean literacy.
3. Spring-to-Sea Water Stewardship Campaigns.
4. Promoting best practices in water-related citizen engagement initiatives.

The below paragraphs detail the action plans for each of the aforementioned points:

3.1 Promoting the standardisation of methods and data management of citizen-generated data

Work package (WP) 1 specifically aims to develop and implement standardised methods and data management practices for citizen-science initiatives focused on freshwater and marine ecosystems, addressing key contemporary challenges in the field. A central objective is to harmonise data collection and management protocols, ensuring that data gathered by diverse citizen-science efforts are of high quality, comparable, and integrable across different initiatives, thereby enhancing the overall impact of these efforts on environmental monitoring and stewardship.

In addition to these technical goals, we are deeply committed to upholding citizen privacy and ethical considerations. Thus, we will discuss and recommend clear guidelines on data ownership, ensuring that contributors retain rights over their data while enabling its responsible use in scientific research. The framework will also address the ethical implications of data collection, emphasising transparency, informed consent, and the protection of sensitive information, following FAIR data principles.

The integration of AI and advanced data analytics will be explored to optimise data processing, identify patterns, and predict environmental trends. However, this will be done with a keen awareness of the risks associated with data exploitation and algorithmic bias. Actions undertaken in this work package will therefore include safeguards to ensure that AI applications are used ethically and equitably, preventing misuse and ensuring that the benefits of citizen-science data are shared fairly among all stakeholders.

By addressing these contemporary issues, the work package not only aims to enhance the scientific value of citizen-science data but also to build trust and empower communities, making citizen science a robust and ethically sound tool for advancing our understanding and management of freshwater and marine ecosystems.

To address the aforementioned challenges, WP1 has undertaken the organisation of **three co-creative workshops** to engage the wider community in discussing the following topics:

1. Legal issues regarding citizen generated data for the water domain.
2. Online workshop on ethical issues and water stewardship.
3. Citizen-science data technical standardisation, data quality and reliability, including its integration into relevant EU policy instruments.

The workshops were recorded and shared with the wider community. Main discussion points and findings of these workshops were summarised and integrated into three draft white papers that were subsequently published on Zenodo (Table 2). The OTTERS consortium has reached out to the larger academic and expert communities to contribute to these drafts, with the possibility of authorship in the final published versions of these white papers.

Table 2: Three draft white papers published on Zenodo on standardisation of citizen science in the water domain (External links - on Zenodo - are embedded).

The role of citizen science within WFD and SDGs, and how to incentivize the collaboration with environmental regulators	Link
Riparian Ecotone Citizen Science	Link
Citizen Science as a contributor to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive implementation	Link

OTTERS also organised an expert workshop at the ECSA Conference 2024 to discuss standardisation issues and share our outlook with interested attendees. Subsequently, another specialised workshop for methods used and integration of citizen science for monitoring riparian vegetation was organised, recorded, and disseminated on the project’s website and social media channels.

Finally, in expert group discussions, the absence of a specialised working group within the European Citizen Science Association was highlighted. The OTTERS consortium members have thereby undertaken the creation of such a working group ([Aquatic Ecosystems and Citizen Science](#)). The working group, open to the inclusion of any interested parties, will hold regular meetings to help define and promote standards and best practices in citizen science for both freshwater and marine ecosystems.

3.2 Increasing ocean literacy

The OTTERS WP4 focuses on enhancing ocean literacy in schools by engaging educators in the co-creation of educational materials and activities. Through a series of co-design workshops, a summer school, and training sessions, we aim to empower school teachers and educators with the knowledge, tools, and confidence to integrate ocean literacy into their teaching practices. By actively involving educators in the design process, we ensure that the resulting materials are both pedagogically sound and tailored to the specific needs of different educational contexts.

A key component of this work package is the development of easy-to-use guidebooks that will provide practical guidance on how to incorporate water-related citizen science as project-based learning within school curricula. These guidebooks will be designed to be accessible to educators at all levels of experience, offering step-by-step instructions, case studies, and best practices. The goal is to make it simple for teachers to engage students in meaningful, hands-on learning experiences that not only enhance their understanding of ocean and water-related issues but also foster a sense of stewardship for the environment.

The workshops and training will also serve as platforms for professional development, where educators can share experiences, collaborate on innovative teaching strategies, and build a community of practice around ocean literacy. By creating these opportunities for collaboration

and learning, we aim to support educators in their ongoing professional growth and to inspire them to become champions of ocean literacy in their schools and communities. Engaged teachers and schools will be encouraged to join the network of European Blue Schools [\[link\]](#) to become part of a larger community of similar interests, share experiences, achievements, and be informed with future opportunities.

In conjunction with the European Blue Schools Initiative, the OTTERS project has engaged and will continue to investigate joint activities and synergies with all European and international projects aimed at increasing ocean literacy and student engagement in citizen science, including but not limited to projects such as ProBleu, Blue Minds 4 Teachers, BlueLights, SHORE, the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO, and WWF's Adopt a Beach Campaign. Furthermore, the WP will find synergies with the co-designed umbrella campaigns to integrate as many students either in ongoing citizen science projects or to start new ones in the chosen pilot countries.

To these aims, the WP will organise a number of workshops to highlight relevant ongoing projects and efforts, identify intra- and extracurricular materials to integrate citizen science in teaching, disseminate funding opportunities for schools to develop water-related projects, and promote joint school activities within the Spring-to-Sea Stewardship Campaigns or similar efforts. OTTERS have also organised a summer school to help train middle and high school teachers from across Europe to integrate citizen science in their curricula. Many local co-design workshops (in native languages) will be organised with educators in the pilot countries to train teachers and help integrate schools into the Spring-to-Sea Stewardship Campaigns and receive feedback from educators to improve educational toolkits on what works well and what needs improvement. Lastly, where necessary, guidebooks (in local languages) will be developed and distributed to schools in the pilot countries to function as a step-by-step roadmaps for such activities. These materials, in addition to a citizen science MOOC that will be developed, will also be made available on the Citizen Science Resource Hub and on several educational and citizen-science related platforms for wider accessibility.

Ultimately, this work package seeks to create a lasting impact on how ocean literacy is taught in schools. By equipping educators with the resources and skills they need to effectively integrate water-related citizen science into their curricula, we aim to inspire the next generation of students to become informed and active participants in the stewardship of our oceans and freshwater resources. This initiative not only contributes to the broader goals of environmental education but also helps to cultivate a culture of sustainability and responsible citizenship among young learners.

3.3 Spring-to-Sea Water Stewardship Campaigns

Spring-to-sea water stewardship campaigns that target ongoing projects and active citizens will be developed through co-creation sessions. A result of these sessions would be updated toolkits, the initial versions of which are to be prepared by 21C Consultancy, with the input from the citizens and other parties interested to contribute to the development of the toolkit. After an inventory of completed and ongoing CS initiatives was prepared within WP1, three geographic and thematic pilots were chosen to run these campaigns.

The pilot countries were chosen to design ‘template’ campaigns over a wide-array of topics and realities, ranging from a country (Italy) with an abundance of citizen science projects in the water domain to one (Armenia) where such initiatives are in their infancy. Diverse topics (water quality, plastic pollution, etc.) were also chosen to develop unique campaigns focusing on different challenges and methods of standardisation.

The development of umbrella campaigns in Italy, Portugal, and Armenia aims to create a cohesive framework that unites ongoing freshwater and marine-related citizen science projects under three thematic areas. The campaigns will drive synergistic efforts across the pilot countries, allowing for a more coordinated approach to citizen science. Each country’s unique environmental challenges and strengths will be leveraged to ensure that the campaigns are locally relevant while contributing to broader regional and global goals in environmental monitoring and stewardship.

In Italy, the campaign will capitalise on the country’s rich tradition of community involvement in environmental initiatives, particularly in monitoring water quality. The focus will be on enhancing existing freshwater programs, integrating citizen-science data with government and academic efforts to create a more comprehensive understanding of water-related issues. The campaign will promote collaboration between local communities, schools, and research institutions, fostering a sense of shared responsibility and encouraging more widespread public participation.

Portugal’s campaign will concentrate on marine litter, reflecting the country’s extensive coastline and its critical role in European marine ecosystems. Citizen-science projects in Portugal will be aligned under this theme, encouraging the collection of data and promoting discussions on prevention of pollution and ecosystem restoration. By uniting these efforts, the campaign will not only provide valuable insights into marine health but also raise awareness about the importance of biodiversity conservation. The campaign will also seek to engage coastal communities, highlighting the connection between healthy marine ecosystems and sustainable livelihoods. Ongoing engagement with projects like Plastic Pirates will help promote methods and best practices developed in these projects to be adopted and implemented on a larger scale, thereby further expanding the network of plastic monitoring created within the initiative.

In Armenia, the campaign will address the impacts of water pollution on freshwater resources, namely the largest lake in the Southern Caucasus, Lake Sevan. A critical resource for a landlocked country, Lake Sevan has undergone a process of eutrophication and has exhibited harmful algal blooms during the past decade. By emphasising the theme of healthy catchment equals a healthy lake, the campaign will aim to educate the public on the importance of every daily action and sustainable water management in the face of a changing climate, while also advocating for stronger policies and interventions at the national level.

These umbrella campaigns will not only enhance the effectiveness of individual citizen-science projects but also promote a wider environmental awareness across the regions. By combining efforts and resources, the campaigns will amplify the impact of citizen science, turning localised data collection into powerful tools for regional environmental management. Furthermore, the

campaigns will serve as a model for scaling up citizen science in other regions, demonstrating how coordinated, theme-based approaches can lead to more significant and sustainable outcomes in environmental stewardship.

3.4 Promoting best practices in water-related citizen engagement initiatives

The aforementioned activities and campaigns will aim to serve as models and catalysts to promote a synergistic and standardised approach to scaling up citizen science and promote water stewardship. However, namely a number of toolkits and resources will be developed in the process that is helpful to highlight here again:

- **The Citizen Science Resource Hub:** will be a platform on ECSA's website that will host all materials prepared throughout the OTTERS project and beyond,
- **Three white papers** to help standardise citizen science methods and data management for both freshwater and marine domains,
- Creation of **the ECSA Working Group: Aquatic Ecosystems and Citizen Science** to engage a wider community of experts in the promotion of standards and best practices,
- **A MOOC for educators** on how to integrate citizen science as a project-based learning in school curricula,
- **Three pilot Spring-to-Sea Stewardship Campaigns,**
- **Guidelines and toolkits** aimed at different stakeholders on how to design and run regional citizen science projects based on the co-designing process of the aforementioned campaigns and captured feedback from engaged stakeholders.